

Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) among the Secondary Math Teachers

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Abstract

Integrating digital technologies is found to have a significant positive effect on content and pedagogy hence, this study was conducted to create a new perspective and understanding on the extent of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) among secondary Math teachers to address key instructional domains. The study utilized a descriptive – correlational design employing a total of 26 Math teachers. The teachers filled in a survey questionnaire to describe their understanding of TPACK through the given knowledge indicators: Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), Content Knowledge (CK), Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK), Technological Content Knowledge (TCK), Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) and TPACK. With the given knowledge components, teachers registered a fair extent of TCK; other components are within the range of high extent. PK registered the highest. Statistical test between the teacher’s profile and the overall mean implied that teachers who attended training more frequently tend to have higher extent of TPACK. Further test revealed that there is a correlation between the frequency of training and on TCK (medium), PCK (strong) and TPK (strong) implying a need of training for development and enhancement. Other tests indicated that there is a negative correlation on generation year and TK indicating that “older” teachers tend to have lower confidence on the use of technology in the classroom. Lastly, teaching experiences when tested with the latter resulted in positive correlation suggesting that TK could be developed with constant use and experiences.

Keywords: Teacher profile, Technological Literacy, Training

I. INTRODUCTION

To be able to translate and contextualize information to improve student's understanding and motivation for learning, an effective Mathematics teacher of the 21st century classroom requires a strong specialized knowledge across different cases and structures. This often include, not just on the content of the different Math subject to be taught and the pedagogies that are to be used to effectively deliver the content, but also on the use of digital technologies which has significant effect on both the content and the pedagogy of what they are attempting to teach. It is expected then that as a Math teacher, one should have proficiency in using technology as a tool in improving learning outcomes.

However, as claimed by Niess, et al (2009), *"a few teachers embraced the use of graphing calculators, spreadsheets, and software like Logo and Geometric Supposer"* since *"their knowledge of students' understanding, thinking, and learning in mathematics held to the importance of mastery of skills with paper and pencil prior to using modern digital technologies."* Further, they also claimed that on the recent past years, mathematics teachers' PCK lacks a solid and consistent integration of modern digital technologies such as dynamic geometry tools or advanced graphing calculators with computer algebra systems (CAS); using the said technologies *"for modelling and providing examples, where students imitate the actions and use the technologies for verification, demonstration, and drill and practice."* As such, it is important that deeper understanding of such actions must be made in order to comprehend and find new light on mathematics teachers who do not integrate fully the relative technologies in mathematics instruction.

Much research have made studies with regards to such dilemma but only a handful have tried to enquire about the interconnection of content, pedagogy and technology. However, with the introduction of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK), educational framework as proposed by Koehler and Mishra (2005), the extent of knowledge on the use of

modern digital technologies which includes information and communication technology, thought to have changed the nature of the classroom teaching and learning process, will be recognized.

By doing so, this will provide an avenue for the educational leaders to provide interventions and programs relative to the integration of ICT in Education such as digitization of content learning areas intended for teachers, which happened to be included in Basic Education Research Agenda. By studying factors which may affect the delivery of the content of the lesson such as the knowledge of use of technology in instruction, learning outcomes will be examined more effectively.

Relative to this, the main concept of the study is not just the content and pedagogical knowledge of the teacher but also on technological knowledge which is deemed important considering the demands of the gen - z learners on the use of technology in the classroom as TPACK is based on “framework builds on Shulman’s (1987, 1986) descriptions of PCK to describe how teachers’ understanding of educational technologies and PCK interact with one another to produce effective teaching with technology.” (Koehler and Mishra, 2009). At the heart of the framework is the idea that using technology for teaching requires the understanding of how technology, pedagogy and content support students learning (Forsell, 2011). it involves an understanding of the complexity of relationships among students, teachers, content, technologies, and practices to address major areas needed to ensure high quality instruction. (Archaumbelt and Crippen, 2009). It is an understanding of how a tool can be used - its features, affordances, and constraints – to uniquely support students’ learning of a given curricular topic or concept (Forsell, 2011).

Hence, this study

II. Research Objectives

This research aimed at determining the extent of Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) of secondary mathematics teachers and identify possible factors affecting

such to create a new perspective and understanding in providing new direction of enhancing their skills 21st century skills ready for the post pandemic education.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study made use of descriptive – correlational research design to appropriately answer the research problem at hand. Descriptive statistics were used in determining the extent of TPACK of teachers and correlation was used in determining the relationship of the extent of TPACK and the predetermined profile that could affect them.

Sample

The researchers covered a total of 26 out of 27 math teachers' or 96% participatory rate (absent during the conduct of the study). With this number, more than half of the respondents (61.6%) are millennial and post millennial; 65.2% have teaching experience of more than 4 years; 56.5% of the respondents are only receiving at most 1 training for professional development; and 73.1% are enrolled in their graduate studies.

Data Collection

The survey questionnaire used in gathering the needed data consisted of 47 questions directly lifted from the study of Sahin (2011) entitled *Development of Survey of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK)*. The compositions (number of questions per domain) were as follows: Technological knowledge (15), Pedagogical knowledge (6), Content knowledge (6), Technological Pedagogical knowledge (4), Pedagogical Content knowledge (7), Technological Content knowledge (4), and Technological Pedagogical and Content knowledge (5). Informal interviews and observations were also made by the researchers to determine possible factors that may have decisive effects on the answers of the respondents and to accurately describe the existing reasons for such.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The following tables present various dimensions to which the teachers are demonstrating the TPACK components: Technological knowledge (TK), Pedagogical knowledge (PK), Content knowledge (CK), Technological Pedagogical knowledge (TPK), Pedagogical Content knowledge (PCK), Technological Content Knowledge (TCK); and Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK).

Table 1 indicates the extent to which the secondary math teachers assess themselves through the given TPACK components. It can be noted that teachers demonstrate high extent of knowledge on various components except Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) where the teachers registered a fair extent of knowledge. With the given components, Pedagogical knowledge (PK) registered the highest mean (3.18, high extent).

Table 1: Extent of teacher's TPACK on various components

TPACK component	Mean	Description
Technological knowledge (TK)	3.10	High Extent
Pedagogical knowledge (PK)	3.18	High Extent
Content knowledge (CK)	3.11	High Extent
Technological Pedagogical knowledge (TPK)	2.95	High Extent
Pedagogical Content knowledge (PCK)	3.02	High Extent
Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)	2.75	Fair Extent
Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK)	2.86	High Extent

Table 2 indicates the correlation between the extent of teacher's TPACK and their profile. As noted on the table, there is a significant medium correlation between generation year and Technological knowledge (TK). Frequency of training revealed correlation on Technological Pedagogical knowledge (TPK) (strong), Pedagogical Content knowledge (PCK) (strong) and Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) (medium). Other computed relationships with regards to TPACK components and profile are found to be not significant.

Table 2: Correlation of extent of teacher's TPACK and their profile

TPACK component	Generation	Years of Teaching	Frequency of training	Education
Technological knowledge (TK)	-0.461*	0.472*	0.419	0.171
Pedagogical knowledge (PK)	0.068	0.043	0.364	.0351
Content knowledge (CK)	0.162	0.078	0.380	0.179
Technological Pedagogical knowledge (TPK)	0.010	0.166	0.525*	0.203
Pedagogical Content knowledge (PCK)	0.123	0.065	0.515*	0.106
Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)	0.053	0.206	0.446*	0.107
Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK)	0.213	0.158	0.367	0.008

*significant at .05

**significant at .01

Table 3 summarizes the factors affecting the extent of TPACK of teachers. Access to learning resources remains one of the factors affecting the extent to which the mathematics teachers demonstrate their TPACK components highlighting further the available references for teaching mathematics or the limited or availability of internet connectivity. Limited trainings and seminars has also been identified as factor indicating that limited educational trainings that is specific for teaching mathematics especially on mathematics software pose some effect on their extent of TPACK. Lastly, congested learning competencies in mathematics requiring extended hours of teaching is deemed to have a particular effect at a certain extent.

Table 3: Factors affecting extent of TPACK of secondary math teachers.

Factors	Responses
Access on Learning resources	reference when teaching Mathematics [r21]
	limited access to internet connectivity [r11]
	no connection due to the school's location [r21].
Limited trainings and seminars about technologies in mathematics	more seminars and activities [r20] to attend to give them time to update themselves such as workshops [r16]
	use of Geogebra in enhancing the learning experiences of the students [r1].
	limited trainings [r11]
	educational technology training [r19] especially on various and appropriate mathematics software [r8]
Congested learning competencies	compressed learning competencies [r8]
	too much required time in teaching the learners [r12]

Discussion

According to Coe, Aloisi, Higgins and Majors (2014), TPACK, which has strong correlation to instructional approaches (Muhaimin, et al 2019), is the most impacting significant factor in improving student's outcomes. TPACK comprises of integrated knowledge representing the teacher's accumulated wisdom with respect to teaching practice, pedagogy, students, subject matter and the curriculum (Solis, 2009). As such, it is important that such knowledge must be developed by the teachers to produce quality student outcomes.

While there is a high extent TPACK among the teachers on the different indicators presented, TCK remains at a fair extent attributing to the reduced technological integration due to limited technology tools and access to the internet (Alkhawaldeh and Menchaca, 2014; Ertmer et al. 2012) as cited by Muhaimin, et al. (2019). Further, while there is a very high score in content knowledge, the issue on accessibility may also be the reason why there is a low score of technology – based knowledge of teachers (Muhaimin, et al (2019) indicating that among the seven domains of TPACK, TPK is second to the lowest domain.

In relation to the profile of the respondents, teachers professional development which includes seminars and trainings is found to have a correlation on TPK, PCK and TCK domains. While specific professional knowledge such as mathematical understanding can be acquired in university trainings (Fennema; Romberg, 1999; Grossman, 2008; Morris, Hiebert, Spitzer, 2008), as cited by Olfos, Goldrine, Estrela, (2014), trained teachers have a higher mean score in mathematics assessment as compared to untrained teachers arguing that, (Fennema; Franke ,1992; Darling – Hammond, 2000; Krauss et.al., 2008; as cited by Olfos, Goldrine, Estrela, (2014), expert teachers are not only broader than that of inexperienced teachers, but also more connected and integrated. The results further confirmed that teachers PCK configuration implies trainings in a specific area strengthened by reflexive practice that leads to an effective practice Olfos, Goldrine, Estrela, (2014). With regards to the relationship of TK and generation year, it further confirms that senior teachers do not have good skills of ICT or its integration based on the result of Muhaimin, et al (2019) indicating that there was a statistically varied differences between

the age groups (25 – 35) (36 – 45) (46 – 55) at TPK scores with the younger ages as the highest or that older teachers with more teaching experience were less confident about their Web - based TPACK (Lee and Tsai, 2010).

Lastly, factors affecting extent of TPACK of secondary math teachers emanates from the lack of learning materials that could be used as a reference when teaching Mathematics [r21]. Further, the compressed learning competencies as required by the curriculum limits them from exploring new concepts and theories [r8], taking too much of their time teaching the learners [r12] more than anything else. As such, the teachers needed more seminars and activities [r20] to attend to give them time to update themselves such as workshops [r16] on the use of Geogebra in enhancing the learning experiences of the students [r1]. Moreover, lack of ability in deeper ICT integration [r12] has always been a difficulty to the teachers due to the limited access to internet connectivity [r11] or no connection at all due to the school's location [r21]. Thus some of them finds it hard to use technology [r20] during classroom instruction, though they are willing to attend seminars [r16] and educational technology training [r19] especially on various and appropriate mathematics software [r8] to create a more meaningful and relevant activities and projects [r1].

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

With the given knowledge components of the TPACK framework, teachers have registered a fair extent of TCK indicators. All others are within the range of high extent; PK component registering to be the highest among them. Test of relationship between the profile of the respondents and the overall TPACK implies that those teachers who attend trainings more frequently tend to have higher extent of TPACK. Further test reveals that there existed a correlation between frequency of training and on the component TCK (medium), PCK (strong) and TPK (strong). Other tests indicate that there is a negative correlation on generation year and positive correlation on years of teaching when tested with technological knowledge (TK). The most frequent factor identified by the teachers to be highly affecting their extent of TPACK is

frequency of attending trainings, seminars or workshops. As asserted, it will enable them to update themselves with regards to the use and integration of technology in mathematics instruction.

Within these conclusions, the following recommendations are then drawn:

1. More than half of the teachers are already accustomed to the use of technology. As such, they could serve as “Techno Buddy” to those “older” teachers who have difficulty in using the recent and trending educational technologies.
2. Due to its abstract nature, teachers find it difficult to appropriately find a relevant technology fitted for a specific content. Thus, LAC sessions focusing on the proper utilization of technologies such as Photomath and Geogebra are highly recommended.
3. Training has been found to be significantly affecting the extent of TPACK of teachers, thus the department must invest much on these to create a more holistically developed teacher, ready for the demands of the 21st century classroom.
4. A separate study is highly recommended to the future researchers to explore and evaluate the training programs conducted by the department and their relationship to the extent of TPACK of teachers.

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